

Original Research

The Influence of Green Banking and Green Accounting on Profitability of Banks Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of green banking and green accounting on the profitability of banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2018 to 2022. Using secondary data obtained from the annual and sustainability reports of 30 selected banks, hypothesis testing was performed through panel data regression analysis with EViews 13 software. The results demonstrate that both green banking and green accounting have a significant positive effect on profitability. Green banking practices, such as sustainable financing and operational efficiency measures, contribute to reduced operational costs and attract investors and customers (p-value = 0.0044). Similarly, green accounting, which integrates environmental considerations into financial reporting, enhances transparency, reduce risks, and improve a bank's public image (p-value = 0.0003). These findings highlight that the adoption green banking and green accounting not only supports environmental sustainability but also leads to improved financial performance. This research suggests that Indonesian banks should embrace these practices to ensure long-term profitability while aligning with global sustainability trends.

Keywords: Bank, green accounting, green banking, Indonesia Stock Exchange, profitability.

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Introduction

Environmental concerns, including eco-efficiency and the environmental impact of industrial operations, are garnering increasing attention from a broad spectrum of stakeholders, particularly economic actors. This growing awareness compels businesses to adopt ethical practices that transcend the pursuit of profit, urging them to consider their environmental and societal responsibilities to ensure long-term sustainability. Green banking has emerged as a progressive initiative within the banking sector, aimed at enhancing environmental risk management. It also fosters eco-friendly financing mechanisms, such as investments in renewable energy and sustainable agriculture. Green banking represents more than a superficial “Go Green” campaign; it is a strategic, long-term business model that not only delivers profitability but also yields significant environmental benefits. At its core, green banking seeks to diversify financing portfolios with a focus on environmental sustainability, including investments in renewable energy, energy-efficient technologies, and eco-conscious products (Bai, 2011). Green banking encompasses financial institutions that prioritize sustainability within their operations. These institutions often integrate cutting-edge technologies and digital platforms to reduce the carbon footprint associated with traditional banking activities (Gupta, 2015).

Figure 1. Greenhouse gases measured in million metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e). Data excludes Land-Use Change and Forestry (LUCF)
Source: Boyle (2024)

Indonesia’s carbon footprint has been steadily increasing over the years, highlighting the urgency for all sectors, including banking, to take responsibility for environmental sustainability (Boyle, 2024). While banks, as service-oriented institutions, are often excluded from stringent environmental regulations—particularly in Indonesia—they still hold a critical role due to their substantial profits and influence (Wongso et al., 2023).

Although banks do not directly produce carbon emissions like manufacturing companies, their financial power positions them as key players in driving sustainable initiatives. If green banking and green accounting practices prove to enhance profitability, they could incentivize greater environmental contributions from the banking sector, underscoring the importance of conducting this research.

Green accounting and green banking represent pivotal contemporary business practices aimed at integrating environmental considerations into the core operations of companies and financial institutions (Fajriah et al., 2023). Green accounting entails the systematic measurement and reporting of the environmental consequences of a company's activities, providing a comprehensive evaluation of its ecological footprint. In contrast, green banking encompasses banking practices that prioritize environmental sustainability, such as financing eco-friendly projects and managing environmental risks. The adoption of both green accounting and green banking is driven by the dual imperatives of stakeholder expectations and regulatory mandates, such as Indonesia's Law No. 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, and Bank Indonesia Regulation No. 14/15/PBI/2012 on Bank Asset Quality Assessment. Green banking initiatives, including the proliferation of online and mobile banking services, along with efforts to reduce paper consumption, significantly contribute to fostering environmental sustainability (Nath et al., 2014).

Profitability within the banking sector functions as a vital safeguard against unexpected losses, strengthens capital reserves, and enhances future profitability through the reinvestment of retained earnings. It serves as a measure of a bank's efficiency in generating profits, thus acting as a fundamental indicator of its success. Potential investors meticulously evaluate a bank's operational efficacy and its capacity for sustained profit generation (Owusu-Ansah, 2000). In this study, profitability is quantified using metrics such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), net interest margin (NIM), and earnings per share (EPS). The level of profitability is often a proxy for a bank's overall financial health (Jatana & Jain, 2020). Various factors influence bank profitability, including risk management strategies, operational efficiency, asset quality, interest rate fluctuations, diversification of products and services. Additionally, government regulations, macroeconomic conditions, and the implementation of sustainability practices such as green banking and green accounting play a significant role. In this study, green banking and green accounting have been specifically chosen as exogenous variables. The primary focus is on their direct impact on bank profitability, excluding other potential influencing factors.

The selection of green banking and green accounting as exogenous variables in this research is underpinned by stakeholder theory. This theory asserts that these practices are likely to have a favorable impact on bank profitability, as indicated by key performance metrics such as ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS (Negoro et al., 2023). Furthermore, this choice is reinforced by legitimacy theory, which contends that the adoption of green banking practices can enhance profitability, as measured by ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS. By embracing sustainable and environmentally responsible practices, banks can cultivate legitimacy in the eyes of the public and stakeholders, thereby fostering a positive reputation that translates into improved financial performance (Mousa & Hassan, 2015).

Numerous studies suggest a positive correlation between the adoption of green banking practices and bank profitability (Al Mamun & Rana, 2020; Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013; Hossain & Kalince, 2014; Rachman, 2021). A key factor underpinning this positive relationship is the operational efficiency achieved through environmentally sustainable practices. Banks that embrace sustainability initiatives often optimize resource management, particularly energy consumption, leading to lower operational costs and heightened efficiency. Furthermore, banks that demonstrate a commitment to sustainability are more likely to cultivate a strong reputation among both the public and investors. This enhanced reputation can yield long-term advantages, including an increase in customer base and stronger stakeholder trust. Green banking practices also stimulate innovation in banking products and services, creating new opportunities to attract customers and expand market share. Improved risk management, particularly regarding environmental risks, can mitigate legal and regulatory challenges that might otherwise threaten profitability. Additionally, enhanced access to sustainable capital and more favorable lending conditions further supports the financial sustainability of banks.

Contrary findings have emerged from studies that suggest green banking may negatively impact profitability (Karyani & Obrien, 2020; Siahaan et al., 2021). Furthermore, another study found that green banking has no significant impact on profitability (Putri et al., 2022). The suggestion that green banking adversely affects profitability implies that, while sustainability practices contribute positively to environmental and social responsibility, they may also impose additional operational pressures or costs that could dampen financial performance. Conversely, the observation that green banking does not influence profitability indicates that banks can adopt sustainable practices without compromising their financial outcomes.

Several studies support the notion that green accounting has a positive impact on profitability (Dewi & Narayana, 2020; Putri et al., 2019; Wardianda & Wiyono, 2023). Green accounting positively influences profitability by enabling companies to effectively manage the environmental aspects of their operations. Through green accounting, organizations can evaluate and quantify the environmental impact of their activities, thereby facilitating the implementation of sustainable strategies. This approach can lead to increased operational efficiency, reduced waste, and innovations that enhance resource utilization. Moreover, sustainable accounting practices can bolster a company's reputation among consumers and investors who are increasingly focused on environmental concerns. In sum, prioritizing green accounting can yield long-term advantages, ultimately enhancing the financial performance of the company.

Contrasting results have emerged from studies such as that by Riyadh et al. (2020), which found that green accounting negatively affected profitability, and by Kholmi and Nafiza (2022), who concluded that green accounting had no impact on profitability. These findings suggest that while sustainable accounting practices are geared toward environmental accountability, they may not have an immediate or direct effect on financial performance or company profits. The anticipated positive impact of green accounting may be more long-term or indirectly related to profitability. Additionally, factors such as the initial costs associated with implementing sustainable practices or the absence of sufficient market incentives may contribute to the lack of a direct influence on profitability.

Based on the research arguments presented, a clear research gap emerges. Previous studies exhibit several weaknesses and limitations that warrant attention. Methodological differences, data variations, and divergent regional contexts may undermine the validity and generalizability of their findings. Variations in research design, analytical techniques, and the type and quality of data can yield inconsistent results (Snyder, 2019). Moreover, regional factors, including geographical location, economic conditions, and access to information, can significantly influence the outcomes of such studies. Issues such as inconsistent variable measurement, inadequate control of variables, and data limitations are prominent concerns (Jogiyanto, 2013). Recognizing these shortcomings, this study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by investigating the impact of green banking and green accounting on the profitability of banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). This research offers a more nuanced understanding of these practices within the specific context of Indonesian banking.

This study seeks to address the existing knowledge gap by examining the impact of green banking and green accounting on the profitability of banks listed on the IDX. This focus is particularly important given the limited research concentrated on the Indonesian banking sector, which presents unique characteristics and challenges in implementing sustainability practices (Siahaan et al., 2021). The urgency of this inquiry is underscored by the growing concern over environmental and sustainability issues in Indonesia. Additionally, the financial sector—particularly banks—plays a pivotal role in driving sustainable development. The findings of this study can provide valuable insights for banks, regulators, and other stakeholders. They offer a deeper understanding of how sustainability practices influence profitability within the specific context of Indonesian banking (Rachman, 2021). In doing so, it can inform the development of more effective policies and sustainable business strategies.

Several studies indicate a favorable relationship between the implementation of green banking practices and profitability, with a focus on enhanced operational efficiency and improved reputation (Al Mamun & Rana, 2020; Anggraini et al., 2020; Asfahaliza & Anggraeni, 2022; Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013; Hossain & Kalince, 2014; Pasha & Elbages, 2022; Rachman, 2021). However, divergent findings have emerged from studies that report a negative impact of green banking on profitability (Karyani & Obrien, 2020; Putri et al., 2022; Siahaan et al., 2021). Similarly, in the context of green accounting, while some studies confirm a positive relationship between green accounting practices and profitability (Chasbiandani et al., 2019; Dewi & Narayana, 2020; Pratiwi & Rahayu, 2018; Putri et al., 2019; Wahyuni et al., 2019; Wardianda & Wiyono, 2023; Zulhaimi, 2015), others present contradictory results (Kholmi & Nafiza, 2022; Riyadh et al., 2020). These contrasting findings underscore the existence of a research gap, necessitating further investigation to identify the contextual and methodological factors that may explain these discrepancies. Additionally, there is a pressing need for more comprehensive evidence on the impact of green banking and green accounting on the financial performance of banks in Indonesia.

The novelty of this study lies in its focus on exploring the impact of green banking and green accounting on profitability within the Indonesian banking sector, specifically targeting banks listed on the IDX during the 2018-2022 period. The selection of IDX-listed banks is intentional, given their direct link to Indonesia's capital market (Syiafuddin

& Saleh, 2023). As such, examining these institutions offers valuable insights for investors, regulators, and other stakeholders within the capital market, providing a deeper understanding of how sustainability practices influence financial performance in a key sector of the economy (Tia et al., 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory posits that a company's existence extends beyond serving its own interests, emphasizing the need to create value for its stakeholders (Negoro et al., 2023). Managers hold the responsibility to act in the best interests of all stakeholders, while the board of directors oversees managerial performance to ensure alignment with this objective (Younas, 2022). Stakeholders in the banking sector include employees, customers, lenders, suppliers, competitors, stockholders, investors, government entities, and the broader community. These stakeholders have a legitimate right to access information regarding the company's operations, as effective communication is vital to fostering trust and ensuring accountability (Nielsen & Thomsen, 2018).

The survival of a company is closely linked to the support of its stakeholders, as posited by Hadyarti and Tubagus (2019). Conversely, stakeholders also rely on the company to meet their interests, creating a relationship of mutual dependence (Freeman, 2015). Klik atau ketuk di sini untuk memasukkan teks. Stakeholder satisfaction is determined by three factors: 1) the utility derived from goods and services provided, 2) the perception of organizational justice, and 3) the opportunity costs perceived by stakeholders (Harrison & Wicks, 2013).

In the context of green banking and green accounting, companies use their annual reports as a tool to demonstrate accountability and commitment to stakeholder satisfaction (Nath et al., 2014). These practices reflect an effort to achieve high standards in reporting quality, which in turn enhances stakeholder trust. Within the banking sector, the integration of green banking and green accounting practices reflects a strong commitment to corporate responsibility. These practices demonstrate how banks align their financial performance with broader sustainability goals (Hossain & Kalince, 2014).

Stakeholder theory provides a relevant framework for analyzing the influence of green banking and green accounting on the profitability of banks listed on the IDX. By focusing on these practices, this study aims to explore their impact on both stakeholder satisfaction and overall corporate performance. The theory highlights the importance of balancing the interests of diverse stakeholders while ensuring the long-term sustainability of the company (Freeman, 2015). Applying this perspective allows for a thorough examination of how environmentally conscious banking practices contribute to profitability, thereby benefiting stakeholders and enhancing the company's financial resilience (Hadyarti & Tubagus, 2019).

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory posits that companies strive to align their operations with the values and norms considered legitimate by society (Deegan, 2014, p. 344). Legitimacy reflects a

psychological state of alignment or allegiance from individuals or groups, which is highly influenced by environmental and societal cues (Singh & Walsh, 2022). To gain, maintain, or enhance their legitimacy, companies frequently engage in social and environmental disclosures (Mousa & Hassan, 2015). These efforts are rooted in the concept of a social contract, where companies are expected to conform to societal values and stakeholder expectations to ensure their continued survival and success (Oxibar & Déjean, 2007). As such, legitimacy theory is a valuable framework for understanding corporate motivations and behaviors, particularly in relation to societal and environmental responsibilities (Mousa & Hassan, 2015).

The adoption of green banking and green accounting practices aligns closely with legitimacy theory, as these practices signal that banks are environmentally conscious and socially responsible rather than solely profit-driven (Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013). By demonstrating a commitment to sustainability, banks can enhance their legitimacy, fostering a positive image among stakeholders, including investors. This perception of responsibility can stimulate increased investment activities, as investors are more inclined to support institutions that prioritize environmental stewardship and social responsibility (Pasha & Elbages, 2022).

In the context of banks listed on the IDX, legitimacy theory underscores the importance of aligning corporate practices with socially accepted norms and expectations (Deegan, 2014, p. 344). Banks that actively implement green banking and green accounting demonstrate their dedication to environmental sustainability, thereby reinforcing their legitimacy in the eyes of society and stakeholders. These practices not only help banks maintain their social contract but also enhance stakeholder trust and confidence. Consequently, such legitimacy-driven efforts can lead to increased investment and improved profitability, as banks are perceived as both responsible and forward-thinking entities (Mousa & Hassan, 2015).

Figure 2. Theoretical framework

Hypotheses

The Influence of Green Banking on Profitability

Stakeholder theory asserts that companies must provide value not only for themselves but also for their stakeholders (Freeman, 2015). Green banking practices are believed to positively impact profitability, measured by ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS, by demonstrating social and environmental responsibility. These practices build trust and support from stakeholders, enhance reputation, and expand customer bases, ultimately fostering a conducive environment for profitability growth (Bai, 2011).

Legitimacy theory suggests that companies strive to ensure their activities align with societal norms and expectations (Deegan, 2014). Green banking practices establish

legitimacy by showcasing a commitment to sustainability, which enhances stakeholder trust and investor confidence. This alignment can positively influence financial performance, as stakeholders prefer engaging with environmentally responsible banks (Mousa & Hassan, 2015).

Numerous studies have highlighted a positive relationship between implementing green banking practices and increased profitability, emphasizing benefits such as greater operational efficiency and an enhanced reputation (Al Mamun & Rana, 2020; Anggraini et al., 2020; Asfahaliza & Anggraeni, 2022; Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013; Hossain & Kalince, 2014; Pasha & Elbages, 2022; Rachman, 2021). Nonetheless, contrasting evidence exists, with some research indicating that green banking may negatively affect profitability (Karyani & Obrien, 2020; Putri et al., 2022; Siahaan et al., 2021). These mixed findings expose a critical research gap, particularly in understanding how contextual factors, such as regional market dynamics and regulatory environments, influence the relationship between green banking and profitability. This highlights the need for further investigation in the Indonesian banking sector.

H₁: Green banking positively influences profitability.

The Influence of Green Accounting on Profitability

Hadyarti and Tubagus (2019) emphasized that a company's survival relies on stakeholder support, while Freeman (2010) highlighted the mutual dependence between companies and stakeholders. Stakeholder theory suggests that green accounting positively impacts bank profitability, measured by ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS, by integrating environmental and social considerations into financial reporting. This transparency enhances trust and satisfaction among stakeholders, including shareholders and regulators. It fosters a favorable environment for the bank, improving its reputation and expanding its market share.

According to legitimacy theory, green accounting strengthens corporate legitimacy by demonstrating a commitment to transparent environmental reporting, aligning with societal expectations (Nielsen & Thomsen, 2018). This alignment builds trust among stakeholders, positively influencing investment decisions and financial performance (Mousa & Hassan, 2015).

In the realm of green accounting, some studies demonstrate a positive link between green accounting practices and profitability (Chasbiandani et al., 2019; Dewi & Narayana, 2020; Pratiwi & Rahayu, 2018; Putri et al., 2019; Wahyuni et al., 2019; Wardianda & Wiyono, 2023; Zulhaimi, 2015), while others report conflicting findings (Kholmi & Nafiza, 2022; Riyadh et al., 2020). These disparities underline a significant research gap, particularly in understanding the contextual and operational factors that mediate the relationship between green accounting and profitability. This warrants further exploration within the Indonesian banking sector to address these inconsistencies.

H₂: Green accounting positively influences profitability.

Methodology

This study employed an associative quantitative approach, which is designed to examine the relationships between two or more variables (Snyder, 2019). Specifically, it investigated the impact of variable X on variable Y. A quantitative methodology was applied for hypothesis testing, focusing on the likelihood of erroneously rejecting the null hypothesis (Jogiyanto, 2013). The data utilized in this study were sourced from the annual reports of banking institutions listed on the IDX for the period 2018 to 2022, which were accessible for download on the official websites of the respective banks. This study analyzed key variables including green banking, green accounting, and profitability, with control variables such as bank size, age, and type. The research was conducted between June and July 2024, during which annual reports of banking companies were collected and analyzed. A purposive sampling technique was employed, with selection criteria including listing status, availability of annual reports, disclosure of green banking and accounting information, and consistent profitability. As a result, the sample included 150 observations from 30 banks over a five-year period, fulfilling the minimum requirement of 100 observations necessary for panel data regression analysis.

In this study, several key variables were defined and measured to assess their impact on profitability within the context of green banking and green accounting. Green banking, as defined by Bank Indonesia, refers to banking practices that promote sustainability in both funding and operations. It was measured using the Green Banking Disclosure Index (GBDI), which gauges the extent to which green banking practices are disclosed in annual reports (Handajani, 2019). Green accounting is characterized by the integration of environmental costs and benefits into accounting practices (Saputra et al., 2021). It was measured by analyzing expenditures on environmental initiatives and corporate social responsibility (CSR) funds as reported in financial statements. Profitability, representing a company's ability to generate profit, was measured using various profitability ratios, including ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS (Durguti et al., 2020).

To account for potential confounding factors, control variables such as bank size (capitalization), age (years since establishment), and type (State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) vs. non-SOEs) were incorporated (Fathinna & Pangestuti, 2016). The data analysis process involved multiple stages. Initially, descriptive analysis was performed to summarize and characterize the collected data, providing a solid foundation for subsequent analyses. Following this, a panel data regression model was formulated, with profitability as the dependent variable. Green banking and green accounting served as independent variables, while bank size, age, and type were included as control variables. This approach facilitated the examination of the relationships between the key variables and profitability, while controlling for potential confounders. To ensure data reliability and validity, potential biases in data collection were addressed through rigorous methodological safeguards, including researcher triangulation to cross-verify and correct the data (Jogiyanto, 2013).

Findings

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics provide an overview or description of data based on measures such as the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values. According to the results presented in Table 1, the dataset used in this study comprises 150 observations, which can be explained as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	GB	GA	ROA	ROE	NIM	EPS	SIZE	AGE	TYPE
Mean	0.526	5.54E+11	1.958	9.341	6.112	143.950	8.03E+13	51.866	0.233
Median	0.523	2.59E+09	1.665	8.530	4.815	99.800	1.57E+13	50.000	0.000
Maximum	1.000	1.49E+13	13.580	31.20	48.840	882.520	1.05E+15	127.000	1.000
Minimum	0.142	10000000	0.040	0.140	-3.520	0.290	8.12E+09	4.000	0.000
Std. Dev.	0.187	2.00E+12	2.037	6.784	7.109	169.991	1.95E+14	29.673	0.424
Skewness	0.446	4.799663	3.404	0.725	4.771	1.982	3.205134	0.944	1.260
Kurtosis	4.245	27.80619	17.670	3.067	26.001	7.605	12.64472	3.521	2.590
Sum	79.047	8.31E+13	293.830	1401.180	916.840	21592.56	1.20E+16	7780.000	35.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.236	5.98E+26	618.802	6857.653	7531.983	4305660	5.65E+30	131197.3	26.833
Observations	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

The implementation of green banking (GB) shows an average score of 0.526984, indicating a fairly good adoption, though with significant variation, as some banks exhibit minimal implementation. Green accounting (GA) reveals an average environmental expenditure of IDR 554 billion, but the high disparity suggests inconsistent commitment among banks. The return on assets (ROA) averages 1.96%, with a wide variation ranging from 0.09% to 13.58%, indicating uneven profitability across banks. Return on equity (ROE) averages 9.34%, with substantial variation, reflecting differing performance among banks. The net interest margin (NIM) averages 6.11%, yet its uneven distribution shows a stark contrast in efficiency, with some banks performing exceptionally well while others lag behind. Earnings per share (EPS) averages IDR 143.95, but many banks fall below this threshold, highlighting disparities in profitability. Bank size (SIZE) shows an average market capitalization of IDR 80.3 trillion, with a large gap between large and small banks. The average bank age (AGE) is 51.87 years, indicating substantial experience, though there are both newer and older institutions. Finally, the majority of banks are non-state-owned (TYPE), signaling the dominance of the private sector.

The study reveals significant variation in the adoption of green banking and green accounting practices among banks listed on the IDX, with moderate overall adoption. However, there are notable disparities, consistent with literature on the uneven integration of sustainability in banking (Gupta, 2015; Nath et al., 2014). The variation in profitability indicators (ROA, ROE, NIM, EPS) aligns with previous findings suggesting mixed effects of green banking on financial performance (Al Mamun & Rana, 2020; Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013). Furthermore, the dominance of non-state-owned banks and their market capitalization and age support stakeholder theory, emphasizing the role of reputation in driving profitability (Mousa & Hassan, 2015). These disparities underscore

the need for a deeper understanding of the impact of sustainability practices in Indonesia's banking sector.

Panel Data Regression Analysis Results

In this study, the dependent variable indicators of profitability (ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS) were calibrated into a single variable using the transformation $\text{LOG}(\text{ROA}+\text{ROE}+\text{NIM}+\text{EPS})$ in EViews. This transformation simplifies the analysis by consolidating multiple profitability measures into a unified metric, thereby requiring only a single regression model. The use of the logarithmic transformation not only normalizes the data and mitigates the influence of extreme values but also enhances the model's stability and interpretability. By combining these indicators into one, the approach streamlines the regression process, improving efficiency and ensuring a more focused evaluation of profitability. The outcomes of the Common Effect Model (CEM) test, performed using EViews 13, are as follows:

Table 2. Common effect model test results

Dependent Variable: LOG(ROA+ROE+NIM+EPS)				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 10/24/24 Time: 20:23				
Sample: 2018 2022				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 30				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 150				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-4.756243	1.631463	-2.915323	0.0041
GB	1.609478	0.556692	2.891148	0.0044
LNGA	0.095754	0.025618	3.737764	0.0003
LNSIZE	0.179281	0.059549	3.010630	0.0031
AGE	0.010422	0.003057	3.409261	0.0008
TYPE	0.682375	0.235673	2.895430	0.0044
R-squared	0.491062	Mean dependent var		4.325557
Adjusted R-squared	0.473391	S.D. dependent var		1.460392
S.E. of regression	1.059775	Akaike info criterion		2.993169
Sum squared resid	161.7298	Schwarz criterion		3.113594
Log likelihood	-218.4876	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.042094
F-statistic	27.78847	Durbin-Watson stat		0.418655
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The t-test results for Hypothesis 1 reveal that green banking has a positive and statistically significant impact on profitability in banks listed on the IDX during the 2018-2022 period, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.0044, which is below the 0.05 significance threshold. The positive regression coefficient of 1.609478 further indicates a direct positive relationship between green banking practices and profitability, thereby supporting the first hypothesis. Similarly, the t-test for Hypothesis 2 demonstrates a significant positive effect of green accounting on profitability, with a p-value of 0.0003,

which is below the 0.05 threshold. The regression coefficient of 0.095754 confirms a positive correlation between green accounting practices and profitability, validating the second hypothesis. Regarding the control variables, the t-test results show that bank size, age, and type all exert a positive and significant influence on profitability, with p-values of 0.0031, 0.0008, and 0.0044, respectively, all below the 0.05 significance level. The positive regression coefficients of 0.179281, 0.010422, and 0.682375 suggest that larger banks, older institutions, and various bank types are positively associated with higher profitability, indicating that these control variables significantly and positively impact the profitability of IDX-listed banks during this period.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

In the results of the common effect model, the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.491062, corresponding to a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.700758. This R² value of 49.1062% indicates that the combined impact of green banking, green accounting, and the control variables (bank size, bank age, and bank type) accounts for approximately 49.11% of the variation in profitability. To effectively convey the key results, the table is presented as follows:

Table 3. Key results

		Effect	Significance	Contribution
Main variables	Green banking	Positive	0.0044	49.11%
	Green accounting	Positive	0.0003	
Control variables	Bank size	Positive	0.0031	
	Bank age	Positive	0.0008	
	Bank type	Positive	0.0044	

Discussion

The Influence of Green Banking on Profitability

These findings of this study align with the tenets of stakeholder theory, emphasizing that green banking practices not only enhance environmental sustainability but also improve financial performance by fostering trust and support from stakeholders, including the public and regulatory bodies (Negoro et al., 2023). These practices contribute to a bank's credibility, enhancing its reputation and attracting a larger customer base. This aligns with previous research that supports the positive influence of green banking on profitability, as evidenced by indicators like ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS (Al Mamun & Rana, 2020; Anggraini et al., 2020; Asfahaliza & Anggraeni, 2022; Bhardwaj & Malhotra, 2013; Hossain & Kalince, 2014; Pasha & Elbages, 2022; Rachman, 2021). From a stakeholder perspective, environmentally responsible banks are more likely to attract investor support, customer loyalty, and favorable government policies, creating an environment that supports profitability.

Similarly, the findings support legitimacy theory, which posits that organizations seek to align their actions with societal norms and expectations (Deegan, 2014, p. 344). Green banking practices, by demonstrating a commitment to social and environmental

responsibility, help banks enhance their legitimacy and build trust among stakeholders. This legitimacy, in turn, fosters greater investor confidence and customer loyalty, positively influencing profitability (Mousa & Hassan, 2015). However, despite the robust positive relationship observed in this study, it contradicts the findings of some studies that suggest green banking has no significant effect on profitability (Karyani & Obrien, 2020; Putri et al., 2022; Siahaan et al., 2021). These conflicting results may arise from variations in research methodologies, sample sizes, and the banking contexts analyzed. For example, factors such as the level of market maturity, regulatory frameworks, and the degree of integration of green practices in banking operations may all influence the outcomes of such studies.

This study demonstrates the positive impact of green banking on profitability but underscores the need for further research to resolve conflicting findings in the literature. A deeper exploration of contextual factors, such as banking models, regulatory environments, and stakeholder engagement, could clarify the reasons for these discrepancies. Future research should reconcile these differences to provide a more nuanced understanding of the conditions under which green banking practices drive long-term profitability.

The Influence of Green Accounting on Profitability

The findings of this study align with stakeholder theory, which posits that a company's survival and success are contingent upon the support of its stakeholders (Hadyarti & Tubagus, 2019). According to this theory, green accounting practices enhance profitability by demonstrating a bank's commitment to environmental and social responsibility. By providing transparent information about the environmental impact of its operations, green accounting fosters trust and satisfaction among key stakeholders, such as shareholders, regulators, and the broader public. As a result, banks that adopt these practices are likely to strengthen their reputation, expand their market share, and improve financial performance by securing stakeholder support. This is consistent with the notion that fostering stakeholder trust is integral to achieving long-term profitability in line with stakeholder theory (Freeman, 2015).

Similarly, the findings support legitimacy theory, which suggests that organizations seek to align their actions with societal norms and expectations (Singh & Walsh, 2022). Green accounting practices help banks signal their commitment to socially and environmentally responsible practices, which, according to legitimacy theory, enhances their legitimacy in the eyes of society and stakeholders (Mousa & Hassan, 2015). This enhanced legitimacy, in turn, leads to increased stakeholder engagement, including favorable investment decisions, and ultimately boosts profitability, as indicated by key financial metrics like ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS. By adopting green accounting practices, banks align themselves with societal expectations, fostering trust and support from stakeholders, which positively influences financial performance.

These findings are consistent with prior research showing a positive relationship between green accounting and profitability (Chasbiandani et al., 2019; Dewi & Narayana, 2020; Pratiwi & Rahayu, 2018; A. M. Putri et al., 2019; Wahyuni et al., 2019; Wardianda & Wiyono, 2023; Zulhaimi, 2015). However, conflicting studies suggest no significant

relationship between green accounting and profitability (Kholmi & Nafiza, 2022; Riyadh et al., 2020). These discrepancies may arise from differences in the sample populations, methodologies, and the extent to which green accounting practices have been integrated into the operations of the companies studied. For example, the varying stages of green accounting implementation and the regulatory environments in which banks operate could contribute to the differing results observed in the literature.

In the context of Indonesia, the limited adoption and understanding of green accounting and green banking practices further complicates the relationship between these practices and profitability (Jogiyanto, 2013). Many companies in Indonesia view green accounting as a passing trend or formality rather than a strategic tool for improving organizational performance. This misunderstanding likely hinders the effective integration of green accounting practices within banks, limiting their potential to drive profitability. However, when properly implemented, green accounting can enhance a bank's legitimacy and credibility, promoting transparency and trust among stakeholders. In Indonesia, as banks align more closely with global sustainability expectations, green accounting practices could serve as a key driver of long-term profitability (Wahyuni et al., 2019).

The contrasting findings in the literature highlight the need for further research to explore how green accounting influences profitability across different contexts. Factors such as the maturity of green banking practices, regulatory environments, and stakeholder engagement may shape outcomes. Future studies should examine these factors in greater depth to reconcile discrepancies and clarify the impact of green accounting on profitability, especially in emerging markets like Indonesia.

Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence on the influence of green banking and green accounting on the profitability of banks listed on the IDX from 2018 to 2022. The results indicate that both green banking and green accounting exert a positive and significant impact on the profitability of these banks during this period. The enhancement of green banking practices contributes to improved profitability by reducing operational costs, increasing efficiency, and attracting investors and customers who prioritize sustainability. Similarly, the adoption of green accounting practices fosters profitability by ensuring greater transparency in managing environmental impacts, which helps mitigate financial risks and strengthens the bank's reputation among stakeholders. In addition to these primary variables, control variables such as bank size, age, and type also exhibit a positive and significant effect on profitability. This suggests that larger banks, those with a longer operational history, and state-owned enterprises (SOEs) tend to experience higher profitability within the IDX-listed banking sector during the 2018-2022 period. These findings highlight that the adoption of green banking and green accounting not only supports environmental sustainability but also enhances financial performance. The research suggests that Indonesian banks should embrace these practices to ensure long-term profitability while aligning with global sustainability trends. This study also calls on policymakers to strengthen regulations and incentives that promote sustainable financial practices within the banking sector.

Recommendations

This study has several limitations that warrant consideration. First, the measurement of green banking practices is prone to researcher subjectivity, as indicators are interpreted differently across contexts. To address this, future research should employ standardized frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) or ISO 14001, accompanied by validity tests such as confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), to ensure consistency and objectivity.

Second, the lack of official green banking guidelines in Indonesia results in inconsistent measurement practices. To mitigate this, the Financial Services Authority (OJK) should establish clear standards to facilitate uniform implementation across banks. Integrating these guidelines into banking operations will enhance comparability and transparency in green banking practices. Banks should be encouraged to integrate green banking policies into their strategic planning processes, ensuring that sustainability goals are aligned with business objectives. Practical strategies could include incentivizing green loan products for eco-friendly projects, incorporating green criteria into credit risk assessments, and fostering partnerships with environmental organizations to enhance CSR initiatives.

Additionally, the voluntary nature of green accounting indicators causes variability in reporting. Future studies should focus on developing mandatory indicators to improve transparency and ensure more accurate representation of environmental performance.

Lastly, while key profitability indicators like ROA, ROE, NIM, and EPS are considered, other important metrics such as Cost to Income Ratio (CIR), Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR), and Non-Performing Loan (NPL) are omitted. Future research should incorporate these alongside environmental indicators to provide a more comprehensive analysis of profitability. New profitability metrics like Environmental Cost Efficiency (ECE) and Sustainability Profit Margin (SPM) should also be explored to assess the financial impact of sustainability initiatives.

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